

Development of silver nanoparticle-based bioadhesive films for the treatment of soft tissue infections in the oral cavity*

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Abstract

The application of transparent bioadhesive films is an aesthetic and patient-friendly solution for promoting the recovery of infections affecting the oral mucosa (e.g., on the lips, gums, and cheeks). Targeting the causative agent(s) of such infections is an even better alternative, offering not only protection, pain relief, and reduction of spreading but also actual healing. This study aimed to investigate the antiherpetic, antifungal, and antibacterial potential of a recently obtained and highly potent active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) derived from the complexation of nanosilver with chlorhexidine when formulated into a bioadhesive polymeric film. The primary targets of investigation were selected in accordance with the prevailing aetiology of oromucosal infections (OMIs), and they included Herpes simplex virus 1, *Candida albicans*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus mutans*, and *Streptococcus oralis*. Furthermore, the activity of the formulation was assessed against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli* as potential causative agents of complicated and hard-healing secondary OMIs. The results indicated weak antiviral and virucidal activity against HSV-1, pronounced antifungal activity against *C. albicans*, and a strong and broad-spectrum antibacterial activity of the test films, thus suggesting their potential applicability in the local therapy of various oral cavity infections.

Keywords

Antimicrobial mucoadhesive films, chlorhexidine complex, herpes virus, oral candidiasis, oromucosal dosage forms

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Introduction

Oromucosal infections (OMIs) represent a heterogeneous group of pathological conditions of the oral cavity and the oropharynx. They most commonly manifest as localized lesions, although the severity may range and escalate to diffuse and invasive forms that impact the patients' quality of life or even lead to life-threatening complications (Bandara and Samaranayake 2019). OMIs can be classified according to their etiology (viral, bacterial, or fungal) or the localization—e.g., gingivitis, stomatitis, glossitis, pharyngitis, tonsillitis, or cheilitis. Regardless of the causative agent(s), it is common that OMIs arise along with compromised immunity; their incidence increases in patients undergoing chemotherapy, radiotherapy, or parenteral nutrition, as well as in elderly and chronically ill patients (Gültekin et al. 2024; Eichhorn et al. 2025). Herpesviridae viruses are the most frequent cause of viral infections in the oral cavity. Eight serotypes are predominant, including herpes simplex types 1 and 2 (HSV-1 and HSV-2), varicella-zoster virus (VZV or HHV-3), Epstein-Barr virus (EBV or HHV-4), cytomegalovirus (CMV or HHV-5), and human herpesviruses HHV-6, HHV-7, and HHV-8. The viruses of the Herpesviridae family are characterized by their ability to establish latency and cause recurrent infections. They may induce oral herpes (cold sore), herpetic gingivostomatitis, or oropharyngitis, as well as benign, premalignant, or malignant lesions of the oral mucosa (Fatahzadeh 2017; Bandara and Samaranayake 2019; Santosh and Muddana 2020). Bacterial causes of OMIs include *Streptococcus pyogenes* (pharyngitis and tonsillitis), *Streptococcus mutans* (dental plaque, dental caries), and *Streptococcus* spp. (spp. oralis and sanguinis; dental plaque, contribute to biofilm formation), *Treponema* spp. (oral plaques, endodontic infections, periodontal disease, necrotizing ulcerative gingivitis), and *Fusobacterium* spp. (periodontal disease, necrotizing ulcerative gingivitis) (Fu et al. 2022; Mohammed 2023). Bacterial infections are most often of a complex nature and occur as secondary events following preceding viral infections. Other bacteria, other than the normal oral microbiota (e.g., *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*), may also contribute to complicated bacterial infections in the oral cavity under specific circumstances, such as local trauma, after a tooth extraction, or following surgical procedures (Eckert et al. 2005; Al Khamis et al. 2024). Fungal infections primarily involve oral candidiasis (thrush), caused by *Candida* spp., with *Candida albicans* being the most common causative agent. Oral mycoses also frequently occur when the normal microbiota is disrupted or when the immune system is compromised (Fangtham et al. 2014; Sivabalan et al. 2014; Millsop and Fazal 2016; Mushtaq and Shafi 2022).

The standard therapeutic approaches for the treatment of OMIs usually target the specific causative agent; they include the application of antiviral agents (acyclovir and valacyclovir), antifungals (nystatin, fluconazole, ketoconazole, and itraconazole), or antibiotics (amoxicillin,

erythromycin, clindamycin, and metronidazole) (Vigneswaran and Muller 2019; Ribeiro et al. 2024). For mild forms of OMIs, chlorhexidine (CXD)—a broad-spectrum local antiseptic with a biguanide structure—is also widely administered in the form of mouthwashes and gargle solutions, gels, toothpastes, throat sprays, and others. Products containing CXD typically range in active concentrations from 0.1% to 2%, and when applied for an extended period, they can lead to tooth staining, tartar buildup, temporary taste disturbances, and damage to the oral mucosa. Another important drawback of CXD is that it possesses a relatively limited spectrum of antimicrobial activity, with its ineffectiveness being recognized against mycobacteria, bacterial spores, non-enveloped viruses, and some fungi (McDonnell and Russell 1999; Silvestri and McEnery-Stonelake 2013; James et al. 2017; Najmudin et al. 2023).

In the search for more potent, broad-spectrum, and low-dose-effective antimicrobial agents, we recently obtained a complex of CXD with silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) and established a synergistic action against several microbial strains (Ivanova et al. 2023; Ivanova et al. 2024). AgNPs generate significant scientific interest due to their pronounced activity against viruses, bacteria, and fungi. Their primary mechanism of action involves the release of silver ions, which interact with the microbial cell membranes, leading to membrane destabilization and subsequent cell destruction. Smaller AgNPs ($\leq 10\text{--}20$ nm) are also known to be able to interact with DNA, proteins, and lipids, ultimately resulting in cell death; however, the latter mechanism is related to increased cytotoxicity (Ivanova et al. 2018; Adeyemi et al. 2020; Rodrigues et al. 2024; Idris et al. 2024). The conjugation of “green”-synthesized AgNPs with CXD has so far demonstrated multiple benefits, such as an improved antimicrobial, antiviral, and antitumor spectrum of activity (Gholami et al. 2022; Ivanova et al. 2023; Ivanova et al. 2024; Ivanova 2025; Steckiewicz et al. 2025). Therefore, in the current study, we focused our investigations on developing a local dosage form to deliver the conjugated active complex to oromucosal lesions, hypothesizing that such development may provide a non-invasive, patient-friendly, and universal solution for fighting OMIs of various origins.

Materials and methods

Materials

Silver nitrate (>99.9%) and sodium hydroxide (>98%) were purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific, Oxford, UK. CXD as a diacetate salt hydrate ($\geq 98\%$, Mw 625.55 g/mol) was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich, Burlington, MA, USA. Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) (80–120 cps) was supplied by Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA. Ammonio methacrylate copolymer (type B) (Eudragit® RS 100) was kindly gifted by Evonik Industries AG, Darmstadt, Germany. Acyclovir {ACV,

[9-(2-hydroxyethoxymethyl)-guanine}] was graciously provided by the Deutsches Krebsforschung Zentrum, Heidelberg, with a stock concentration of 3 mM in DMSO. All organic solvents were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich, USA, at analytical grade.

Cells and culture reagents—Madin-Darby bovine kidney (MDBK) cells were obtained from the National Bank for Industrial Microorganisms and Cell Cultures in Sofia, Bulgaria. The cells were cultured in DMEM growth medium (Gibco, Grand Island, NY, USA), supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (Gibco BRL, USA), 10 mM HEPES buffer (AppliChem GmbH, Darmstadt, Germany), and antibiotics (100 IU/mL penicillin, 100 µg/mL streptomycin). Incubation was performed in a HERA cell 150 incubator (Heraeus, Hanau, Germany) at 37 °C with 5% CO₂, and cells were passaged twice a week.

Virus—Herpes simplex virus type 1, Victoria strain (HSV-1), obtained from Prof. S. Dundarov at the National Center of Infectious and Parasitic Diseases in Sofia, was replicated in confluent monolayers of MDBK cells using a maintenance solution. Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM) from Gibco BRL, Paisley, Scotland, UK, supplemented with 0.5% fetal bovine serum (Gibco BRL, Scotland, UK) and antibiotics (100 IU/mL penicillin and 100 µg/mL streptomycin). Following incubation at 37 °C in a 5% CO₂ incubator, the viral yield was frozen at –80 °C. The infectious titer of the stock virus was determined to be 10^{8.5} CCID₅₀/mL.

Microbial strains and culture media—*Candida albicans* ATCC® 10231, *Escherichia coli* ATCC® 25922TM, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC® 25923™, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC® 10145™, *Streptococcus oralis* ATCC® 9811TM, and *Streptococcus mutans* ATCC® 35668™ (as MicroSwabs®), Brain Heart Infusion (BHI) broth (HiMedia, India), and Blood Agar (HiMedia, India)—were supplied by Ridacom, Bulgaria.

Mucosal explants—porcine buccal mucosa explants—were obtained in a certified slaughterhouse (Varna, Bulgaria) from a pig weighing 80–90 kg and aged 7–8 months. The tissue was dissected by pathologists using forceps and a scalpel and transported to the laboratory on ice. The mucosal explants were microscopically observed for any defects. All eligible pieces were frozen in pairs in physiological saline at –22 °C and used within 2 months of collection.

Methods

Synthesis of the active complex

The active complex (Ag-CXD) was derived by the complexation of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) with chlorhexidine diacetate (CXD), based on a recently established and optimized production protocol (Ivanova et al. 2023). Briefly, AgNPs were obtained via “green” reduction of silver ions with green tea phenolic extract. This was done by extracting and purifying green tea polyphenols and subsequently adding a precisely optimized amount of them

in the form of an alkalized (pH 8.0) aqueous solution to a silver nitrate 2 mM solution. The particles formed upon gentle manual mixing at ambient temperature. After being purified via a dialysis technique, they were subsequently conjugated with CXD via electrostatic surface adsorption, as a 0.38% w/v solution of the positively charged drug was added to the negatively charged silver nanosuspension in a 1:2.3 v/v ratio. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS), Laser Doppler Electrophoresis (LDE), X-ray diffraction, and UV-Vis spectroscopy were used to characterize the morphology, hydrodynamic diameter, zeta potential, crystal structure, and surface plasmon resonance of the resultant nanoparticles (Ag-CXD complex), respectively.

Formulation

The active complex was formulated into bioadhesive films by using the Petri-casting technique. A stock solution of HPMC (sol. A) was prepared by first dispersing the cellulose derivative in Ethanol absolute and then adding 15% v/v Ag-CXD (in the form of an aqueous-based conjugated silver nanosuspension—sol. B) to form a viscous, transparent, yellow-brown solution (sol. AB). A stock solution of Eudragit® RS (sol. C) was obtained in a laboratory hood by dissolving the methacrylate copolymer in dichloromethane and mixing it with sol. AB in a 1:4 ratio under continuous stirring at 500 rpm on a magnetic stirrer, IKA® C-MAG HS 4, Germany. Finally, glycerin was added, and the volume of the organic mixture (sol. ABC) was adjusted to 100% with Ethanol absolute in a measuring cylinder prior to casting. In more detail, the composition is presented in Table 1. By maintaining moderate ventilation in the hood, the active ABC solution was poured into previously weighed Petri dishes of 44.2 cm², 63.6 cm², or 100.0 cm² (Fig. 1); a proportion of 0.1 mL solution for 1 cm² area was kept. The films were left under the induced airflow for 4 h to allow fixation and complete evaporation of the organic phase. Afterwards, the Petri dishes were closed, sealed with Parafilm®, and stored in a refrigerator until further use.

Quantification

Ag-CXD quantification was carried out spectrophotometrically on a T60 UV-Vis spectrophotometer (PG Instruments, United Kingdom), equipped with UVWin 6.0 software, by using the standard curve method. For this purpose, the UV-Vis spectra of AgNPs, CXD, and Ag-CXD were scanned in the wavelength range between 200 and 600 nm. Standard calibration curves were obtained in Ethanol 70% w/v at two of the absorption maxima of the active Ag-CXD complex: 1) at $\lambda = 260$ nm, a peak attributed to CXD and boosted by the silver nanoparticles' organic “cap” (linear in the concentration range between 1.89 and 45.20 µg/mL; R^2 0.9999); and 2) at $\lambda = 444$ nm, a peak observed exclusively as a result of the silver nanoparticles' surface plasmon resonance—SPR (linear in the concentration range between 3.50 and 140.00 µg/mL; R^2 0.9994).

Table 1. Composition of bioadhesive films with Ag-CXD.

Compound	Concentration				
	In sol. A, % _{w/v}	In sol. B, % _{w/v}	In sol. C, % _{w/v}	In sol. ABC, % _{w/v}	In film, µg/cm ² [% _{w/w}]
Ag-CXD	–	18.3 × 10 ⁻²	–	18.3 × 10 ⁻³	18.3 [0.33]
HPMC	3.0	–	–	2.0	2000.0 [36.11]
Eudragit [®] RS	–	–	6.0	1.0	1000.0 [18.06]
Glycerin	–	–	–	2.52	2520 [45.50]

Theoretical mass of a film with an area of 44.2 cm²: 244.8 mg (244 792.9 µg).

Figure 1. Petri-casting technique for the production of Ag-CXD-loaded bioadhesive films.

The active content in the formulation was assessed as three films from a batch of 44.2 cm² (independent measurements; $n = 3$) were individually decomposed in Ethanol 70% w/v—a “good” solvent for both polymers and the active complex. First, the films were allowed to swell in a small quantity of the solvent for 60 minutes. Then, stirring was initiated, and the obtained solution was quantitatively transferred into a volumetric flask, where a final dilution up to 25 mL was carried out. The absorbance of the test solutions was measured at $\lambda = 260$ nm and $\lambda = 444$ nm, and each measurement was performed in triplicate (technical replicates; $n = 3$). The concentration of Ag-CXD was calculated simultaneously based on both assays—as a function of the CXD concentration established at $\lambda = 260$ nm and as a function of the AgNP concentration recorded at $\lambda = 444$ nm. The active content in the films (A) was presented as a percentage of the theoretical content.

Uniformity of dosage units

To evaluate the uniformity of single doses in a batch, the recommendations of the European Pharmacopoeia for solutions and solids (freeze-dried in a final single-dose container were followed (Council of Europe 2023).

Thereupon, the mass variation (MV) method applies. The mass of ten individual units (independent measurements; $n = 10$) was recorded to calculate their estimated active content by using equation 1 (Eq. 1):

$$x_i = w_i \times \frac{A}{\bar{W}} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where x_i is the individual estimated content; w_i is the individual mass of the dosage unit; A is the content of active substance, expressed as a percentage of the label claim; and \bar{W} is the mean of individual masses. Next, the Acceptance Value (AV) was calculated as shown in Eq. 2:

$$AV = |M - \bar{X}| + k \cdot s \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where \bar{X} is the mean of individual estimated contents expressed as a percentage of the label claim; M is a reference value ranging from 98.5 to 101.5, depending on the deviation of \bar{X} from the label claim; k is the acceptability constant (k equals 2.4 for sample size 10); and s is the sample's standard deviation (SD). The acceptance criteria for solid, semi-solid, and liquid dosage forms were considered, i.e., $AV \leq 15.0$ and no individual content of the dosage unit of less than $0.75 \times M$ or more than $1.25 \times M$.

Mucosal retention and estimation of wash-out time

The approximate time of retention and washout of the bioadhesive films from the mucosa was estimated through the following multi-step protocol: 1) buccal mucosa explants were defrosted, and circular cuts of 3.14 cm² were made with the aid of an aluminum cap for a penicillin bottle as a template and scissors; 2) the rubber gaskets of the same caps were removed and used to fixate the mucosal pieces; 3) the so-prepared disks with mucosa were left soaked in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) 7.2 until further use; 4) pieces of the test films were obtained with the same shape and size as the buccal mucosa explants by using the same template; 5) the bioadhesive films were carefully applied onto the mucosa; 6) the samples were inserted in Dissolution Apparatus 2 (paddle apparatus), as each vessel contained 500 mL of PBS 7.2 preheated to $37 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \pm 0.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; 7) a rotation of the paddles of 30 rpm was initiated; 8) the disks were retrieved from the medium every hour for observation, and photographs were taken when visible changes tended to occur. The experiment was performed in three independent repetitions ($n = 3$). Fig. 2 illustrates the proposed methodology.

Figure 2. Methodology for evaluation of mucosal retention and washout time.

Anti-*HSV-1* activity

Test sample preparation

A 0.018% w/v concentration of the active Ag-CXD complex (total active concentration of 183 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, corresponding to AgNPs 70 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and CXD 113 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) was restored from a test film with a defined area by first hydrating it and then diluting the viscous liquid obtained with distilled water in a volumetric flask. In more detail, this was done by using a piece of bioadhesive film with an exact surface area of 100.0 cm^2 (wherein the active concentration is 18.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) and final dilution up to 10.0 mL in a volumetric flask. The stock colloidal solutions of AgNPs and Ag-CXD were also tested for reference.

Cytotoxicity assay

Confluent monolayer cell culture seeded in 96-well plates (Costar®, Corning Inc., Kennebunk, ME, USA) was treated with 0.1 mL/well supported medium containing decreasing concentrations of test samples. The cells were incubated at 37 °C and 5% CO_2 for 48 h. After microscopic evaluation, the medium containing the test sample was removed, and the cells were washed and incubated with Neutral Red (NR; Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH, Germany) at 37 °C for 3 h. After incubation, the NR dye was removed, and the cells were washed with PBS. Then, 0.15 mL/well desorbing solution (1% glacial acetic acid and 49% Ethanol in distilled water) was added. The optical density (OD) of each well was read at 540 nm in a microplate reader (Biotek Organon, West Chester, PA, USA). The 50% cytotoxic concentration (CC_{50}) was defined as the concentration that reduces the cell viability by 50% compared to the untreated controls. Each sample was tested in triplicate (technical replicates; $n = 3$), with four wells for cell culture on a test sample. The maximum tolerable

concentration (MTC) was determined by the concentration of the active agent at which the cell monolayer is not affected and appears as it does in the untreated control.

Determination of infectious viral titers

The cells were cultivated in 96-well plates. After the formation of a confluent monolayer, the cells were infected with 0.1 mL viral suspension in tenfold falling dilutions. After 1 h of adsorption, the non-adsorbed virus was removed, and 0.1 mL/well of supporting medium was added to the cells. The plates were incubated at 37 °C in a CO_2 incubator (Radobio Scientific Co., Ltd., Shanghai, China) for 2 days. Cells infected with the maximum concentration of the virus and demonstrating the maximum cytopathic effect (cultivated under the same conditions as the viral control) were used as control. The infectious viral titer was determined by microscopic monitoring of the cellular monolayer and determination of the cytopathic effect (CPE). Visually defined CPE was confirmed by the NR uptake assay. Viral titers were expressed as lg IU (infectious units) (CCID_{50}) / 0.1 mL.

Antiviral activity assay

A CPE inhibition test was used for the assessment of the antiviral activity of the test samples. A confluent cell monolayer in 96-well plates was infected with a 100-cell culture infectious dose of 50% (CCID_{50}) in 0.1 mL. After 1 h of virus adsorption, the non-adsorbed virus was removed, and the test sample was added in various concentrations; the cells were incubated for 48 h at 37 °C. The CPE was determined using an NR uptake assay, as described in the previous section, and the percentage of CPE inhibition for each concentration of the test samples was calculated using Eq. 3:

$$\% \text{CPE} = \frac{[\text{OD}_{\text{test sample}} - \text{OD}_{\text{virus control}}]}{[\text{OD}_{\text{toxicity control}} - \text{OD}_{\text{virus control}}]} \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where $\text{OD}_{\text{test sample}}$ is the mean value of the ODs of the wells inoculated with the virus and treated with the test sample in the respective concentration, $\text{OD}_{\text{virus control}}$ is the mean value of the ODs of the virus control wells (without the

test sample in the medium), and $\text{OD}_{\text{toxicity control}}$ is the mean value of the ODs of the wells not inoculated with the virus but treated with the corresponding concentration of the test samples. The 50% inhibitory concentration (IC_{50}) was

defined as the concentration of the test sample that inhibited 50% of viral replication when compared to the virus control. The selectivity index (SI) was calculated from the CC_{50}/IC_{50} ratio.

Virucidal assay

Samples containing virus (10^5 CCID₅₀) and the test sample at its MTC were combined in a 1:1 ratio and subsequently stored at room temperature for different time intervals (15, 30, 60, 90, and 120 min). Then, the residual infectious virus content in each sample was determined by applying the end-point dilution method (Reed and Muench 1938) and recording the difference in viral titers Δ lg (delta log) of treated and untreated samples.

Statistical analysis

The values of CC_{50} were calculated using non-linear regression analysis (GraphPad Software, San Diego, California, USA). The values were presented as means \pm SD from three independent experiments ($n = 3$). The differences' significance between the cytotoxicity values of the samples and the reference substance ACV, as well as between the effects of the test samples on viral replication, were determined by Student's t -test, considering significant p -values of < 0.05 .

Antimicrobial assay

Test sample preparation

A 0.012% w/v concentration of the active Ag-CXD complex (total active concentration of 116.3 μ g/mL, corresponding to AgNPs 44.5 μ g/mL and CXD 71.8 μ g/mL) was restored from a test film with a defined area following the same procedure as described in the above section concerning the antiviral assay. In more detail, this was done by using a piece of bioadhesive film with an exact surface area of 63.6 cm² (wherein the active concentration is 18.3 μ g/cm²) and final dilution up to 10.0 mL in a volumetric flask.

Antimicrobial assay

The antimicrobial activity of the bioadhesive films was assessed against reference strains, including *Candida albicans* ATCC[®] 10231, *Escherichia coli* ATCC[®] 25922, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC[®] 25923, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC[®] 10145, *Streptococcus oralis* ATCC[®] 9811, and *Streptococcus mutans* ATCC[®] 35668. Two-fold serial dilutions of the test solution were carried out in a sterile 96-well culture plate. To each well, 150 μ L of BHI broth was added and it was previously inoculated with 15 μ L of standardized microbial suspension (McFarland 0.5). Afterwards, the samples were incubated as follows: the ones inoculated with *C. albicans*—

aerobically for 48 h at 35 °C; the ones inoculated with *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. oralis*—aerobically for 24 h at 37 °C; and the ones inoculated with *S. mutans*—in a microaerophilic 5% CO₂ environment for 48 h at 37 °C. Positive controls of all microbial strains were set. Ethanol 70% w/v was used for the negative control tests. The minimal bactericidal and fungicidal concentrations (MBC/MFC) were determined by a single bacterial-loop-volume transfer of the test suspensions after incubation on Blood Agar. The so-obtained specimens were incubated once again under the aforementioned conditions. The lowest concentration at which microbial growth was inhibited by 99.9% was reported as MBC/MFC. The assay was carried out with a triplicate repetition of each measurement (biological replicates; $n = 3$) (CLSI 1999; Mah 2014).

Results

Features of the active complex

The Ag-CXD complex was obtained in the form of an aqueous nanosuspension with a total active concentration of 1.83 mg/mL, corresponding to 0.7 mg/mL nanosilver and 1.13 mg/mL CXD. The stock colloidal solution was characterized by an average hydrodynamic diameter of 142.5 nm and a distinctly positive zeta potential ($\zeta +44.59$ mV), foretelling physical stability (Ivanova et al. 2023). These and other key properties of the Ag-CXD conjugates, established in previous studies, are summarized in Fig. 3.

Active content in bioadhesive films

In the investigated wavelength range, two characteristic peaks appeared in the spectrum of the active Ag-CXD complex, viz., at $\lambda = 260$ nm and at $\lambda = 444$ nm (Fig. 4A). As can be seen from the reference spectra of CXD and the non-conjugated silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) in the same figure, the former extremum is a result of the absorption of both the antiseptic drug and the organic matter of catechin derivatives on the surface of the metal nanoparticles. Although being altered and complex, the absorption maximum at 260 nm showed good correlation with the CXD concentration within the CXD-conjugated silver nanosuspension ($R^2 0.9999$), and the standard calibration curve obtained (Fig. 4B) was considered eligible for quantification of active content in the test films. The same conclusion applies to the standard calibration curve obtained at the peak of the SPR— $\lambda 444$ nm ($R^2 0.9994$; Fig. 4B), which was independently used to determine the concentration of AgNPs in the test samples and to cross-check the results from two parallel assays when the total Ag-CXD content was to be estimated.

The results for active content in the formulated bioadhesive films are shown in Table 2.

Figure 3. Results of instrumental analyses characterizing the Ag-CXD complex (Ivanova et al. 2023).

Figure 4. UV-Vis spectra of CXD, AgNPs, and Ag-CXD (A) and standard calibration curves of Ag-CXD in Ethanol 70% w/v at $\lambda = 260$ nm and $\lambda = 444$ nm (B).

Table 2. Active content determination: a parallel UV-Vis quantification based on two calibration procedures at $\lambda = 260$ and 444 nm.

Dosage Unit №	CXD, determined at $\lambda 260$ nm \pm SD, $\mu\text{g/mL}$	AgNPs, determined at $\lambda 444$ nm \pm SD, $\mu\text{g/mL}$
1	21.156 \pm 0.088	13.534 \pm 0.0589
2	21.917 \pm 0.021	15.12 \pm 0
3	19.199 \pm 0.0821	12.960 \pm 0.0583
Mean \pm SD	20.757 \pm 1.402	13.871 \pm 1.119
Estimated Ag-CXD concentration, $\mu\text{g/mL}$	33.615 \pm 2.270*	36.263 \pm 2.925*
Theoretical Ag-CXD concentration in test solution, $\mu\text{g/mL}$		32.354
Active content, % (A)**		107.99%

* The calculation is based on the AgNPs-to-CXD ratio within the conjugated silver nanosuspension; the concentration of AgNPs is 0.7 mg/mL, while the concentration of CXD is 1.13 mg/mL, which corresponds to a total active concentration of 1.83 mg/mL or $18.3 \times 10^{-2}\%$ (as presented in Table 1).

** Expressed as a percent of theoretical (labeled) content; calculated as the average of the values obtained from the two parallel assays—at 260 and at 444 nm.

Uniformity of dosage units

Table 3 presents the results and calculations for the evaluation of uniformity of dosage units following the European Pharmacopoeia methodology. Judging by the AV (≤ 15), the prepared bioadhesive films comply with the pharmacopoeial requirements for uniformity of dosage units. Furthermore, no individual value falls outside the acceptable range between $0.75 \times M$ and $1.25 \times M$, i.e., each examined dosage unit was characterized by an active content from 76.16% to 126.88%.

Mucosal retention and washout time

A complete washout of the films from the buccal mucosa explants occurred between the 4th and 6th hour of the experiment for all samples, demonstrating good adhesiveness and retention and thus potential for ensuring prolonged local action. Fig. 5 illustrates the observations over time; a red arrow points out the last time interval when traces of the formulation were still visible on the mucosal surface. At the end of the experiment, no signs of tissue coloration as a result of the application were noticed with the naked eye.

Anti-HSV-1 activity

To correctly conduct the antiviral experiments in non-toxic concentrations of the test samples, their

influence on the viability of an MDBK cell monolayer was first evaluated. The cytotoxic effect was determined 48 h after the treatment of the cells with the test samples, as this period is required for the virus to exhibit an optimal CPE on the cell line. From the obtained results, it was found that all three samples were significantly more cytotoxic than the reference substance acyclovir (ACV) (Table 4).

After determining the non-toxic concentration range of the samples, their antiviral activity against HSV-1 in MDBK cells was followed. All three samples demonstrated a weak effect on HSV-1 replication with an SI < 5 , with the non-formulated Ag-CXD slightly prevailing over the film-formulated active complex (Table 4). Meanwhile, the CXD-conjugated form was found to eloquently increase the toxicity and antiviral potency of the silver nanoparticles.

The effect of the test samples on the viability of extracellular HSV-1 virions was also examined. When determining the virucidal activity against herpes particles, it was found that in the first investigated time interval (15 min), the effect was insignificant. At 30 min of exposure, AgNPs slightly increased their activity to $\Delta \lg = 1.25$ and remained so to the last examined time interval—120 min. When treated with Ag-CXD in their non-formulated and formulated form, the decrease in viral titer by 60 min was a maximum of $\Delta \lg = 1.0$, and at 120 min it little increased to $\Delta \lg = 1.25$ (Table 5).

Table 3. Measurements and calculations for the determination of dosage units' uniformity.

Dosage Unit №	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
w_p , mg	246.0	227.0	232.4	234.7	248.1	240.2	238.4	225.2	232.2	240.3
W	236.1									
A, %	108.0									
A / W	0.457									
x_p , %	112.9	104.2	106.8	107.7	113.8	110.2	107.7	103.3	106.6	110.3
X	108.3									
M**	101.5									
<i>s</i>	3.3									
<i>k</i>	2.4									
AV	14.7									

* A was derived from the quantification of Ag-CXD in the bioadhesive films.

** M is equal to 101.5 since targeted content per dosage unit (*T*) is 100 percent at the time of manufacture and $\bar{X} > 101.5$ (Council of Europe 2023).

Figure 5. Observations over mucosal retention and approximate time to complete washout of the bioadhesive films from the buccal mucosa.

Table 4. Cytotoxicity and antiviral activity.

Sample	MDBK cell line		HSV-1 (Victoria strain)	
	CC ₅₀ Mean ± SD	MTC	IC ₅₀ Mean ± SD	SI
1. AgNPs	58.5 ± 2.4 µg/mL [*]	7 µg/mL	21.4 ± 1.8 µg/mL [*]	2.7
2. Ag-CXD	3.8 ± 0.8 µg/mL [*]	0.7 µg/mL	0.9 ± 0.03 µg/mL [*]	4.2
3. Ag-CXD-loaded film	4.2 ± 0.4 µg/mL [*]	0.7 µg/mL	1.1 ± 0.06 µg/mL [*]	3.8
ACV	291.0 ± 9.4 µg/mL	-	0.33 ± 0.03	881.8

* $p < 0.001$, when comparing the value of each test sample with the reference substance ACV.

Table 5. Virucidal activity against HSV-1 virions.

Sample	Δlg				
	15 min	30 min	60 min	90 min	120 min
1. AgNPs	1.0	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25
2. Ag-CXD	0.75	0.75	1.0	1.0	1.25
3. Ag-CXD-loaded film	0.75	0.75	1.0	1.0	1.25
Ethanol 70%	8.25	8.25	8.25	8.25	8.0

Antifungal and antibacterial activity

Six opportunistic pathogens were included in the study, among which was one fungal strain—*C. albicans*; two inherent to the oral cavity Gram-positive bacterial species of the *Streptococcus* genus (i.e., *S. mutans* and *S. oralis*); *S. aureus* as one of the most abundant Gram-positive bacteria in humans; and two generally challenging to fight Gram-negative bacteria, i.e., *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*. The results indicated antimicrobial activity of the Ag-CXD-loaded films against all test microorganisms, with *S. oralis* appearing as the most susceptible (MBC:

≤ 1.87 µg/mL or ≤ 0.0002% w/v), followed by *S. aureus* (MBC: 3.75 µg/mL or 0.0004% w/v), *S. mutans* and *E. coli* (MBC: 7.49 µg/mL or 0.0008% w/v), *C. albicans* (MFC: 14.98 µg/mL or 0.0015% w/v), and *P. aeruginosa* (MBC: 59.93 µg/mL or 0.006% w/v). Proof and illustration of the results from the antimicrobial assay are presented in Fig. 6.

Discussion

A silver nanoparticle-based active complex was obtained via surface functionalization of a “green”-synthesized, negatively charged nanosilver suspension (AgNPs) with the positively charged antiseptic drug chlorhexidine (CXD). Indeed, a relatively large hydrodynamic diameter of the particles was registered via DLS analysis (Z-average: 142.5 nm), while the zeta potential fell in the desired stability range (+44.59 mV). On the positive side, it is well known that metal nanoparticles of larger size are characterized by significantly lower toxicity and ensure safer application (Karlsson et al. 2009; Ivanova et al. 2018; Idris et al. 2024). In addition, our previous studies proved the

Figure 6. Antimicrobial activity of Ag-CXD-loaded bioadhesive films.

colloidal stability of the conjugated silver nanosuspension over time and its explicit antimicrobial activity based on the synergistic activity of AgNPs and CXD (Ivanova et al. 2023). From what we know so far, the antimicrobial properties of the complex could be primarily attributed to the gradient release of silver ions and CXD from the particles' surface rather than cellular or tissue uptake of non-decomposed particles. Since bulkier particles could potentially guarantee exclusive local action with minimal risk of transmucosal absorption of silver nanoparticles, our further investigations took direction toward topical administration, as this study presents.

Our current goal was to develop and characterize a semi-solid dosage form to deliver the active complex to oromucosal lesions of infectious origin. Out of aesthetic and biopharmaceutical considerations, the choice fell on oromucosal films; they are usually characterized by simple and reproducible technology, as well as by good physical, chemical, and microbiological stability (Preis et al. 2013; Resende et al. 2024). In general, oromucosal films, along with the majority of bioadhesive formulations for oromucosal administration (e.g., buccal tablets, gels, and films), find application as local as well as systemic drug delivery systems (Gupta et al. 2021). They provide prolonged contact with biological tissues owing to the presence of bioadhesive polymers in their composition. In cases when the polymeric excipients adhere to the outermost mucus layer of the mucosa (as is the case with the current formulation),

the phenomenon of adhesion could more specifically be referred to as mucoadhesion (Avhad et al. 2021). In this study, a simple combination of HPMC and Eudragit RS[®] was selected. The cellulose derivative (HPMC) was intended for the role of a mucoadhesive agent, while the methacrylate copolymer, being swellable and permeable but water resilient, was added to ensure the films' mechanical strength and sustainability. The polymers' ratio, the choice of other excipients, and the production technology were empirically optimized in advance until flexible, infrangible, and non-drying films were obtained. Important considerations for optimization of the films' production technology were also the apparent viscosity and volatility of the active solution for casting and the suction power maintained in the laboratory hood. They were regulated to allow even and easy spreading upon pouring into the Petri dishes, yet fast and complete solidification within a few hours under the induced airflow. The suitability of the proposed technology is supported by the established compliance of the films with the European Pharmacopoeia standards for dosage units' uniformity.

A dual UV-Vis spectrophotometric procedure was proposed for the active content determination in bioadhesive films; a calibration curve was based on the AgNPs' SPR (at $\lambda = 444$ nm), while another—on the CXD absorption, but in a wavelength region where the polyphenolic cap on the AgNPs surface also absorbs— $\lambda = 260$ nm. This was done to cross-check the plausibility of the Ag-CXD quantification

since neither the quantification method is standard or established elsewhere nor is the API a single and defined compound. Both calibration procedures showed linearity of $R^2 \geq 0.999$, which was in the concentration range between 1.89 and 45.20 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ at $\lambda = 260$ nm and in the concentration range between 3.50 and 140.00 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ at $\lambda = 444$ nm. The two methods did not show a statistically significant difference at a 5% threshold ($p = 0.09$), and an agreement could be declared within a $\Delta \pm 15\%$ acceptance range.

A test was carried out to estimate the approximate time of mucosal retention (or time to complete washout) of the films by using buccal mucosa explants for the purpose. The test films demonstrated prolonged retention for up to 4–5 h. It is to be noted that this observation was made *in vitro*, by simulating much more aggressive conditions on a paddle apparatus (rotation of 30 rpm in 500 mL PBS 7.2) than the physiological salivary debit (of around 0.4 mL/min in an unstimulated state and up to 2.0 mL/min in a stimulated state) could provide. Still, the recommendation applies to all oromucosal dosage forms (especially those with sustained drug release) to be administered in time intervals away from eating and drinking (Bácskay et al. 2025). In the case of our development, for which the application site is limited to the oral cavity but not precisely specified, it would be of great importance to the adherence time what the location and size of the lesion to be treated are (e.g., gums, tongue, cheeks, lips, and palate). Since the proposed formulation does not contain any other adhesives except the moderately mucoadhesive (but very well tolerable) HPMC, effective lip adhesion (e.g., for the treatment of cold sores) may require wetting of the film in advance.

The results from the anti-HSV-1 study revealed that the active Ag-CXD complex, as well as the Ag-CXD-loaded films, exert some effect on HSV-1 replication, while the effect on virions was negligible. This observation suggests that the resulting antiviral effect is due to activity manifested inside the infected MDBK cells. Meanwhile, several studies in the literature report that silver nanoparticles

inhibit HSV-1 by blocking viral attachment (by binding to viral surface glycoproteins and virucidal deformation), entry, replication, and spread, with functionalization enhancing antiviral potency and immune modulation (Orlowski et al. 2014; Krzyżowska et al. 2017; Pan et al. 2022; Luceri et al. 2023). Moreover, AgNPs are shown to possess superior broad-spectrum efficacy and synergism with standard antivirals, often outperforming other metal-based nanoparticles, while exhibiting generally low cytotoxicity at effective doses (Cagno et al. 2018; Tomaszewska et al. 2022). However, the AgNPs' antiviral potency is typically greater for smaller particles (often $\leq 10\text{--}30$ nm) and highly dependent on surface ligands that promote interaction with viral attachment proteins (Luceri et al. 2023). In this regard, the larger size and the densely occupied surface of the AgNPs obtained herein may explain the weak antiviral effects and the lack of pronounced virucidal activity. In contrast, the antimicrobial activity of the test formulation was presented as strong and broad spectrum, considering the low minimal effective concentrations for microbicidal action against all test strains. While there are numerous scientific reports on the antimicrobial activity of various AgNPs against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *C. albicans* that support the outcomes of our investigation (including proofs of inhibitory, microbicidal, and antibiofilm effects), this study provides one of the few studies demonstrating activity against the whole listed microbial spectrum, including *S. mutans* and *S. oralis*, at such low active concentrations (Abadi et al. 2013; Liao et al. 2019; Panpaliya et al. 2019; Ahamad et al. 2022; Chegini et al. 2024; Elchaghaby et al. 2024; Barbaresco et al. 2025). The obtained results on antifungal and antibacterial activity suggest that a bioadhesive film formulation could also be obtained in lower active concentrations of Ag-CXD, thus further reducing the toxicity concerns upon oromucosal application and potential swallowing. Table 6 summarizes the MBC/MFC values herein obtained, along with the clinical relevance of each test strain for the occurrence and persistence of OMIs.

Table 6. MBC/MFCs values and clinical relevance of the test strains for the occurrence and persistence of OMIs.

Infectious strain	MBC/MFC, $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Clinical relevance
<i>C. albicans</i>	14.98	The leading cause of oromucosal fungal infections, it causes oral candidiasis primarily upon compromised immunity (Tamai and Kiyoura 2025)
<i>S. aureus</i>	3.75	Contributes to secondary oromucosal infections, particularly in immunocompromised patients, denture wearers, and cases of angular cheilitis or oral abscesses (Campos et al. 2023)
<i>S. mutans</i>	7.49	A normal oral commensal and inhabitant of dental plaque; the primary bacterial pathogen associated with dental caries, contributing indirectly to oromucosal infections by initiating tooth decay that can progress to odontogenic and mucosal inflammation (Mazurel et al. 2025)
<i>S. oralis</i>	<1.87	A common early oral colonizer that contributes to biofilm formation and polymicrobial oromucosal infections, with clinical importance mainly as an opportunistic pathogen (Ren et al. 2024)
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	59.93	A potential contributor to mixed/complicated bacterial infections in the oral cavity under specific circumstances, such as local trauma, after a tooth extraction, or following surgical procedures (Eckert et al. 2005; Al Khamis et al. 2024)
<i>E. coli</i>	7.49	A potential contributor to mixed/complicated bacterial infections in the oral cavity under specific circumstances, such as local trauma, after a tooth extraction, or following surgical procedures (Eckert et al. 2005; Al Khamis et al. 2024)

Conclusion

Oromucosal films were obtained with weak antiviral and virucidal properties against HSV-1, distinct antifungal activity against *C. albicans*, strong and broad-spectrum antibacterial activity, and sustained mucosal retention, thus suggesting their potential applicability in the local therapy of various oral cavity infections. As an API, a silver nanoparticle-based active complex was utilized, after being previously obtained via surface functionalization of “green”-synthesized silver nanoparticles with CXD. The proposed active complex—Ag-CXD—expressed physical stability in colloidal solution and a sufficiently large hydrodynamic diameter, needed to ensure preferential local activity with low risk of particles’ absorption and toxicity. The current study proved that an adhesive polymeric matrix of HPMC and Eudragit RS may efficiently serve as a delivery platform for oromucosal application of the Ag-CXD complex without concealing the antimicrobial activity of the API within the bioadhesive formulation. The proposed composition and technology allowed the establishment of a simple and easy-to-reproduce preparation technique for thin, transparent, and resilient films possessing good mucoadhesive properties and complying with the European Pharmacopoeia standards for dosage units’ uniformity. Still, further *in vivo* studies are needed to confirm the here-established *in vitro* activity and prove the clinical applicability (incl. tolerability and efficacy) of the suggested bioadhesive films.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors’ representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

Use of commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines: Madin-Darby bovine kidney (MDBK) cells were obtained from the National Bank for Industrial Microorganisms and Cell Cultures in Sofia, Bulgaria.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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